

EXPLORING THE POSSIBILITIES OF USING EFFECTIVE BIM TECHNOLOGIES FOR "TOSHTEMIRYOLLOYIHA" LLC ON THE BASIS OF MODERN FOREIGN EXPERIENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6478311>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st April 2022

Accepted: 10th April 2022

Online: 14th April 2022

KEY WORDS

digital construction, building information modelling (BIM), tunnel modelling and management, asset management.

ABSTRACT

Technology has been a strong driver for industrial efficiency in the twenty-first century. Rapid growth in infrastructure projects such as tunnels is synonymous with both disruptive and supportive technologies that automate operations. The sector has rapidly risen to the challenge from buyers demanding a more digitalised experience when looking to (re)design new tunnels. Currently there are projects in the United Kingdom, Greece and Italy investing in tunnels for their transport networks to help commuters to travel quicker. We could argue that construction has evolved because the tunnels developed nowadays are expected to last for several generations but such an argument is count intuitive. Think of having to spend billions of pounds for a tunnel that does not provide an enhanced travel experience and in a few years' time requiring a major investment to remodel in order to operate it. This chapter discusses what, why and how digital construction can add value during the lifecycle of a tunnel.

Technology has been a strong driver for industrial efficiency in the twenty-first century. Rapid growth in infrastructure projects such as tunnels is synonymous with both disruptive and supportive technologies to automate operations. The tunnelling sector has rapidly risen to the challenge from tunnel asset owners demanding more digital design solutions when procuring new tunnels. Currently there are projects in the Russia , Uzbekistan and Asia investing in tunnels to improve transport capacity and help commuters to travel quicker. We could argue that construction has evolved

because the asset developed in now expected to last for several generations but such argument is intuitive. Imagine having to spend billions of pounds for a tunnel that does not provide an enhanced travel experience and in a few years' time requiring a major investment to remodel in order to operate it. Construction cannot afford to remain stuck in past and must transform to improve delivery efficiency and sustainability.

The World Economic Forum (2020) has developed a transformation framework for the construction industry listing 30 measures of best practice. It highlights

three important areas of transformation from its traditional approach. Firstly, it has to be open for innovation so that opportunities from new technologies, materials and tools are exploited to reduce production costs. Secondly, it should consider adopting mechanised and automated production systems alongside offsite construction techniques to speed up the construction process and enhance timely completion of projects in a collaborative environment. However for projects of high complexity such as tunnelling that involves a number of strategic and operational decisions from the client, designers, contractors, the supply side and regulators, BIM can provide a collaborative platform. Through vertical and horizontal collaboration, processes and resources will be optimised to deliver the client's requirements. Inadvertently this generates a significant amount of data, which needs to be integrated and communicated to the stakeholders so that optioned solutions are agreed on and value is created. Digital construction is an adoption of technology driven initiatives that aim to make use of advances in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to enhance integration.

The integration model highlights the need to bring together people, processes, and products of the construction project to deliver value to the client in a more efficient and sustainable way. The third area pivots on the role of project management and the control of costs in the design and planning stages. When procuring projects, contracts are designed to achieve optimum risk sharing across the supply chain with agreed monitoring mechanisms. Lately, the momentum within

construction has shifted from the focus on the top down approach of project delivery to more collaborative approach that seeks to satisfy clients' requirements. Results of embracing digital approaches to construction are increasingly yielding positive results and more projects that would otherwise pose high risk of cost overrun are being delivered timely and on budget. Digitalisation of procurement process through the use of approaches such as e-procurement, e-tender and e-sourcing has increased cooperation between client and contractors because of the confidence developed through sharing of accurate data and clarity of information. This has enabled misunderstanding and barriers of culture to be better managed.

Technology Integration is the use of technology tools in general content areas in businesses in order to allow stakeholders to apply computer and technology skills to learning and problem-solving. Collaboration requires individuals working together in a coordinated fashion, towards a common goal. Arguably Integrated Collaborative Technologies are those tools that can help stakeholders work collectively towards problem solving without considering geographical distance. These technologies could work either in a synchronous (real time) or asynchronous (not real time) manner, so allowing the stakeholders or the team members to share documents or files from anywhere at any time.

The project data must be kept in a secure environment with set permissions in order for stakeholders and project team members to have access from anywhere at any time. In order to achieve this then a common data environment (CDE) needs to be set up. In this environment all project

data need to be correctly labelled based of standard file naming conversions form the ISO standard. This makes searches using metadata easier and saves time wasted on unproductive searches. Having easy but secure remote access also allows for further (project) data analysis that can help to pre-identify any project activities that provide more information about who is involved in the projects (Organisation Breakdown Structure), what each person is expected to deliver (Work Breakdown Structure) and what the cost of each activity is (Cost Breakdown Structure). All the captured and updated data might be used for further analysis with the aim to support any decisions before, during and after completion of the project. Such data analysis could support investor(s) capacity to understand based on evidence whether it is worthy to progress their project idea as well as to pre-identify any risks that can be evaluated in consideration of other factors that may affect the project such as in any political, economic, social, environmental, legislation, technological and sustainability issues.

Data used in tunnelling projects is collected using many different tools such as Laser Scanner, Sensors, inspections, etc., and comes in various formats. All these data sets could be available to stakeholders synchronously i.e. either in real time or not. With the increase in analytical tools for infrastructure maintenance, Big Data analytics is an increasingly area in

construction sector due to high Volume, Value, Variety, Velocity and Veracity generated through the project whole life cycle. Concerns in copyrights for cloud based data and BIM models are beyond the scope of this book. In addition the power of the Internet of Things (IoT) as a network of physical devices, vehicles (suppliers), and other project materials embedded with electronics, sensors, software, actuators and connectivity enables construction asset/building objects to connect and exchange data too.

This will be achieved through enhanced human communication, innovative visualisation, knowledge support and natural interaction and will transform the current working practices to be more competitive in the global market. CoSpaces proposes to validate these collaborative workspaces against three sectors: aerospace, automotive and construction. However, the impact of the technology will go beyond these three sectors due to the generic nature of the technologies. CoSpaces will undertake the ambitious challenge of developing the technical, organisational and human networks to build collaborative workspaces. This will be achieved through a systematic and integrated programme of RTD activities, dissemination, training, demonstration and exploitation activities, led by a consortium of European experts who are committed to this mission.

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